

Optimization Of Accounting Recording Process Using RPA Technology in Multifinance Companies

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Abstract— This study investigates the optimisation process of accounting recording systems within financial institutions, focusing on the role of Robotic Process Automation in multifinance firms. By employing a qualitative exploratory approach through a Systematic Literature Review, the research evaluates the extent to which existing studies have explored five key steps of process optimisation: Tasks and Process Identification, Workflow Redesign, Development and Testing, Implementation, and Performance Monitoring. The findings reveal that Tasks and Process Identification have received the most attention among these steps, while Development and Testing remain the least explored areas. The study highlights the transformative potential of Robotic Process Automation in enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making within financial operations. Furthermore, it provides insights into the challenges and opportunities for improving Robotic Process Automation implementation, suggesting a need for further research in less explored dimensions. This research contributes to understanding the current state of adoption and offers actionable insights for future advancements in the financial sector.

Keywords— Accounting Recording Process, RPA, multi finance, automation, SLR

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's modern age has exposed many different industries to many transformative endeavours. The financial services sector is no exception, and it has adopted numerous essential technologies due to the rapid advancement of technology. Integrating technology into the financial service sector gives an organisation better flexibility and integration between the departments and divisions. For example, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) technology streamlines the process and standardises the information. According to [1], the study reflects the significant relationship between successful ERP systems usage and business performance, and the expanding market of ERP becomes the justification for firms to see technology adoption as a requirement. Another technological example is the Accounting Information System (AIS), which eases the process of identification, recording, and reporting by keeping the work paperless and increasing accuracy. [2], [3]. Recording itself remains tedious, involving many repetitive works across different platforms such as Outlook, spreadsheets, AIS platforms, and the web. The growing volume of work and platform poses a risk of human error and extra costs of hiring if it continues to be done manually.[4], [5]. To counter the growing amount of work accounting will need to be automated, there are variations of automation technologies suggested by vendors, such as Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Internet of Things, Cloud Accounting, Big Data, Blockchain, and Robotic Process Automation[3], [6].

Robotic Process Automation (RPA) is one of the easily accessible advancements that can further transform the realm

of accounting within the scope of automation[2], [7], [8]. The benefits regularly mentioned regarding RPA are improved operational efficiency, accuracy, reduced processing time, and elimination of human error. With all the benefits of RPA, companies are sure that RPA will become the future of their company [7]–[12]. As reported by EY, Forrester projected the global spending on RPA will be as much as \$2.9 billion by 2021[13], as 2021 passed the actual number not too far different from the projection, numbering \$2.65 billion. Another projection published in 2024 projected the growth of RPA in 2032 to be \$81.8 billion[14].

As more and more companies adopt RPA into their business process, the competitive advantage described earlier will be the new norm in the future. Therefore, this study believes and focuses on optimising the accounting recording process in multifinance businesses. Integrating RPA technology becomes a feasible way to optimise workflows and boost overall productivity as multifinance firms struggle with the intricacies of financial transactions and regulatory compliance.

This study aims to investigate how well the optimisation process within the Accounting Recording process is explored with the current research on RPA. Previous scholars have explored the supplementary role of automation and its benefits [15], [16]. However, there are limited guidelines and best practices for optimisation through RPA. This study summarises the exploration of RPA technology and optimises the existing accounting recording procedures.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Accounting Recording

George Lisle defined accounting as the treatment of recording methods that serve all transactions, such as the exchange of wealth and its effect on production, distribution, and exchange[17]. An article by Forbes also defines accounting as the process of recording, classifying, and summarising financial transactions[18]. Each statement highlights the importance of accounting despite the span of more than 100 years. Based on the following definitions, it is arguable that the scope and work of accounting can only expand after the last 100 years as now the role of classifying and summarising is added. Accounting clearly shows the organisation's financial position and performance[18].

The result of accounting recordings is the accounting records, which range from the Transactions, Journal, General Ledger, Trial Balance, and Financial Statements[19]. Among the records, the recording process contributes to the Journal, Trial Balance, and Adjusting Entries [20]. Therefore, the processes are record entry, validation, and readjustment to summarise the activity in general.

B. RPA

Robotic Process Automation (RPA) is defined as a tool to automate business processes both partially or fully with the help of software robots, substituting the required human operator of the previously manual task[21]. RPA is considered one of the future automation tools alongside Artificial Intelligence, Neural Networks, Machine Learning, and others [2], [22]–[24]. Automation is desired as a solution to organisations as it gives them multiple benefits and added value in competition, starting from lower expenses, more reliability, improved efficiency, and better quality[22]. The technology of RPA itself promises fewer human errors and better management over different applications and platforms [4], [5].

C. Multifinance Company

Multifinance is a non-bank financial institution that provides financing for the diverse needs of consumers (B2C) or businesses (B2B)[25]. The multi-finance's financial services include procuring vehicles, heavy machinery, furniture, and electronics. Multifinance does not receive deposits of its customers' capital and provides the financing through loans, which the company maintains and manages the risks. The multifinance sector has seen net financing receivables of Rp 475 trillion, a substantial number per January 2024[26]. As of September 2024, net financing receivables have grown to Rp 501 trillion.

Similar to other sectors, technology usage also contributes to the growth of overall multifinance firms and sectors. The business models of multi-finance rely on their ability to manage assets, monitor loans, and mitigate risks [27]. The usage of technology enables firms to operate efficiently. In effect of adopting technology, less paperwork up to thorough risk analysis could be earned as a long-term benefit.

D. Optimization Process

Optimization is an act, process, or methodology of making something perfect, functional, or practical. A point in optimization is doing more with less, making technology's emergence possible. A fundamental problem that can be seen in accounting is the growing amount of work and requirements which lead to repetitive and time-intensive tasks [5], [8], [9], [28]. Similarly, in the Accounting Recording Process, there are many things to be considered within the activity and processes, for example, record and data entry jobs to ERP, which could be manually done by humans or code the part to become automated input; each solution requires enormous spending. Therefore, the RPA operates on a display level and is a cheaper IT solution. Therefore, the key optimization steps would require tasks and process identification, process redesign, implementation, testing and validation, and performance monitoring [29]. The optimisation process aims to reduce organisational compliance risks and human error.

III. METHOD

This section will discuss and explain the methods and data used by the author in this research.

A. Research Method

The research will be done qualitatively using the systematic literature review (SLR) method. The method is

chosen to enable the author to look at the current exploration of RPA in today's literature landscape. Concerning the topics of optimisation, the method allows the author to collect data from diverse publications by authors and scholars. SLTs are used repeatedly to gain multiple reinforcing statements and claims from different authors.

B. Data Collection

The author uses sources of literature found in the Scopus database, consisting of books, conference papers, and journals, to form the desired compilation of literature. The author uses keywords to obtain well-addressed searches and topics to fulfil the scope.

Keywords Used:

- (("TASK IDENTIFICATION" OR "PROCESS IDENTIFICATION" OR "TASK ANALYSIS" OR "PROCESS ANALYSIS" OR "TASK SELECTION" OR "PROCESS ANALYSIS" OR "REPETITIVE TASK IDENTIFICATION" OR "DATA-DRIVEN PROCESS" OR "PROCESS MAPPING" OR "ACCOUNTING DATA EXTRACTION") AND ("RPA" OR ("ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND accounting AND ("BANKING" OR "FINANCE" OR "FINANCING") OR
- ("WORKFLOW REDESIGN" OR "PROCESS REDESIGN" OR "PROCESS IMPROVEMENT STRATEGIES" OR "OPTIMISING ACCOUNTING PROCESS" OR "WORKFLOW ANALYSIS" OR "WORKFLOW IMPROVEMENT" OR "PROCESS REENGINEERING" OR "WORKFLOW REENGINEERING" OR "LEAN PROCESS IMPROVEMENT") AND ("RPA" OR ("ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND accounting AND ("BANKING" OR "FINANCE" OR "FINANCING") OR
- ("AUTOMATION IMPLEMENTATION" OR "AUTOMATION APPLICATION" OR "RPA IMPLEMENTATION" OR "AUTOMATION DEPLOYMENT" OR "AUTOMATING" OR "RPA Use Case") AND ("RPA" OR ("ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND accounting AND ("BANKING" OR "FINANCE" OR "FINANCING")) OR
- ("TESTING" OR "TEST" OR "DEVELOPMENT") AND ("RPA" OR ("ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND accounting AND ("BANKING" OR "FINANCE" OR "FINANCING")) OR
- ("PERFORMANCE MONITORING" OR "PERFORMANCE MONITOR" OR "MONITORING AUTOMATION" OR "POST-IMPLEMENTATION" OR "PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT" OR "AUTOMATION MONITORING") AND ("RPA" OR ("ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND accounting AND ("BANKING" OR "FINANCE" OR "FINANCING"))
- AND ALL (("JOURNAL ENTRY" OR "RECORD ENTRY" OR "VALIDATION" OR "VALIDATE" OR "RECONCILIATION" OR "READJUSTMENT" OR "ENTRY" OR "ENTRIES" OR "DATA ENTRY" OR "DATA VALIDATION") AND ("RPA" OR "ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION")) AND PUBYEAR > 2018 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND PUBYEAR > 2019 AND PUBYEAR < 2025

Research Steps in the PRISMA method:

Fig. 1. Research Steps

C. Data Source

The author compiled various past publications from the Scopus database and specified the scope of searches using keywords involving the terms related to Optimisation Processes and also terms of the Accounting Recording Processes. The time range of the research scope is 6 years, spanning from 2020 to 2024. Twenty publications are included in the research, as shown in Fig. 1. The author found no publications regarding "Multifinance", "Accounting", and "RPA" in the Scopus database. Only

21 publications up to 2024 cover the Multifinance in Scopus, yet none are related to the research. Considering the niche condition of the topic, the author substituted the term "Multifinance" with the more common terms of "Banking", "Finance", and "Financing", which cover mainly similar services.

TABLE I. DATA SOURCE AND TYPES

Year	Journal	Conf.	Total	Percent (%)
2020	[30]	[31]	2 Pub.	10
2021	[32], [33]	-	2 Pub.	10
2022	[34]-[36]	-	3 Pub.	15
2023	[15], [37]-[39]	-	3 Pub.	15
2024	[16], [30], [40]-[46]	-	9 Pub.	45
Total			20 Pub	100

Based on the 20 publications in the research, there are five general steps of the Optimisation Process: Tasks and Data Identification, Workflow Redesign, Development and Testing, Implementation, and Performance Monitoring. The steps will then be linked to 3 processes within Accounting Recording Processes done by accountants: Record Entries, Validations, and Readjustments.

TABLE II. LINKING STEPS OF OPTIMISATION WITH THE ACCOUNTING RECORDING PROCESS REFERENCES

Optimisation Process by RPA	Accounting Recording Processes			Total
	Record Entry (RE)	Validation (V)	Readjustment (R)	
TPI	[15], [16], [30], [32]-[34], [36], [37], [39], [42]-[46]	[15], [30], [32]-[34], [36], [37], [39], [43]-[45]	[15], [32], [34], [36], [39], [43], [44]	14
WR	[15], [35], [42]	[15], [30], [35], [38], [41], [47]	[15], [35], [38], [41]	8
DnT	[15]	[15]	[15]	1
I	[15], [38], [45]	[15], [38], [45]	[15], [38], [45]	3
PM	[15], [31], [41]	[15], [38], [40], [41], [46]	[15], [38]	6

The explanations of the five steps of optimisation are as follows:

1. Tasks and Process Identification (TPI): The first step is identifying which processes are best optimised among the plethora of processes and the goals of the said processes. [15], [29]
2. Workflow Redesign (WR): The process of analysing the current process and pointing out areas for improvement. [29], [37], [38]
3. Development and Testing (DnT): The development and testing of the area of improvement could be done. It is perceived that quick iteration could happen between the development and testing as RPA is a lightweight IT project, as several researchers claim. [15], [34]

4. Implementation (I): Once the desired test results have been achieved and the improvements validated. The official implementation and deployment will be done. [15], [29], [37]
5. Performance Monitoring (PM): The optimisation did not stop there as continuous improvement and more areas for future refinement will be identified. Another important action is implementing continuous knowledge sharing regarding past RPA and present improvements to avoid knowledge loss due to employee turnover. [29], [48]

The Explanations of the Accounting Recording Processes:

1. Record Entries (RE): Record Entries can be found within Journalizing, also defined as the activity of entering data into a journal. [20]
2. Validation: (V): Validation can be found within the activity of Trial balance, defined as an activity to prove the mathematical equality to debits and credits after posting. It is also able to uncover errors made during the record entries. [20]
3. Readjustment (R): Readjustment or adjusting entries is an activity to ensure the recognition of expenses and revenues that follow the required principles. It also has the role of reworking from the previously mistaken entries. [20]

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Therefore, after analysing the gathered kinds of literature, the author found that RPA usage during the 5 years of research is still on the level of complimentary or supplementary[42]. As described by [16], RPA found its place in the organisation's usage; however, it has not become a disruptive technology. It means that the arrival of RPA has not yet changed the game. Yes, it can optimise the work to become more efficient, but its usage remains optional. Nonetheless, the adoption of RPA remains popular as the requirement grows. The growing volume of work, interfaces, websites, and applications influence its use. The author found that the most mentioned positive aspects of RPA technology are the flexibility of performing rule-based tasks and accessing multiple third-party apps and websites as described by [11], [12], [49], [50].

In mapping, Most of the RPA-related publications cover the identification of journal entry tasks [15], [16], [30], [32]-[34], [36], [37], [39], [42]-[46]. The validations and readjustments came from audit-related papers and the reconciliation process choice for RPA projects. [16], [36]. Understandably, the rationale behind the endorsement of RPA usage in the recording processes is that multiple scholars [34], [35], [37], [42] have shown RPA effectiveness in record/data entry jobs and simple processes. Most researchers agree that data entry jobs are prone to human errors and are highly repetitive [43], [44], [46], [47]. Therefore, task identification remains the main focus in today's RPA landscape, especially the simpler ones.

Workflow redesign is mentioned in most of the works of literature found in the SLR [15], [30], [35], [38], [41], [42], [47]. In this context, the literature compares what the prior processes perform and the new processes, as well as breakdowns in detail of which robots perform processes and

which are done manually by humans. Getting into the details of the processes in bank XYZ, the bank identified their process of conducting reconciliation manually. They design the RPA to conduct reconciliation with the help of spreadsheets and replicate functions such as HLOOKUP and VLOOKUP, mimicking the human's movement for the process. Despite the perfect resemblance of human movements, the bank acknowledges the robot's limitation for cognitive tasks. As the term "Garbage In, Garbage Out" goes, the robot will assume all given data are correct, causing a few shortcomings if the processed data is false. After the bank reconciliation process, the robot will produce a report summarising the reconciliation [38].

A publication on development and testing [15] described the nature of the RPA project as a lightweight IT project. It translates to shorter duration, complexity, and resources during the development and testing phase. Therefore, they further present the cutting-edge benefits of RPA, which could easily "integrate" multiple third-party tools and legacy systems without touching the coding, with the other sources claiming that RPA works best with agile methods[40]. However, the development process might require multiple iterations to gain assurance of the project. It also described the idea of composing RPA pilots as prior deployments. The nature of the pilot robot is suitable for demonstration, testing, and validating the functionality of the RPA. It is recommended by [15], [36] that the pilot RPA should be executed for several months to give assurance to the processed data.

Among the implementation of RPA [15], [38], [45]. The papers highlight the case revolving around the implementation of RPA and include concerns, requirements, and effects. The highlighted concerns of RPA implementation mention insufficient governance and internal controls, maintenance and oversight of running RPA solutions, lack of knowledge regarding RPA, and the potential loss of expertise. An example from the case of Bank XYZ, which has implemented reconciliation RPA, the bank should have preserved and documented the business process that was performed by robots. The highlighted requirement spans from knowledge sharing to the acceptance level from human users. Lastly, RPA implementation's effects include user satisfaction, increased information quality, cost-effectiveness, and added net benefits.

All projects must end with periodic evaluations and monitoring [15], [31], [38], [40], [41], [46]. The implementation phase is not the end goal of the whole endeavour. RPA requires scaling, and it can perform more tasks and benefit organisations. It is possible that a perfectly tailored RPA suddenly faces problems due to circumstances in the system or environment. Adding to the plethora of research papers, [48] mentions the threat of knowledge loss due to the dependence on robots and employee turnover. The author also seeks to highlight the consideration of ever-changing conditions and interfaces that could hinder the robot's ability to perform tasks; therefore, a proactive stance on RPA improvement and maintenance is encouraged [49].

V. CONCLUSION

Within the financial sectors similar to multi-finance, the optimization of accounting, especially in the recording process, is well explored. The exploration is mainly in the area

of task and process identifications. However, the development and testing areas require more improvement and exploration. Regarding RPA, there are frameworks created by multiple scholars [15], [35], [46]. Nevertheless, a mutually agreed framework that encourages governance remains lacking. As for the multi-finance sector, optimising RPA brings benefits such as increased accuracy and added efficiencies.

In summary, the five steps of optimisation mentioned above show the current state of explorations into the dimensions of RPA in financial sectors, and past publications show multiple benefits and positive outcomes from using RPA as an optimisation. It is demonstrated and strengthened by various past writings and articles being provided.

The research, of course, is not without flaws. The limitation of this research came from the number of publications covering RPA in multifinance accounting processes. The lack of data on multi-finance also sends a message for future research to conduct a qualitative approach with interviews and questionnaires to users and project owners of the RPA. As mentioned before, the optimisation process is correlated to the employee's acceptance, which differs based on their background. Therefore, future global research on how financing firms work worldwide must examine the common grounds presented.

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